

The effectiveness of advertising campaigns on social media in influencing consumers purchasing decisions: Brand Image.

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Abstract

Our study examines the impact of influencer marketing on brand image. With social media's rise, this strategy has gained momentum, aiming to align brands with values and lifestyles that resonate with target audiences. Despite its popularity, the effectiveness of influencer marketing remains debated.

The study proposes three hypotheses regarding the influence of marketing on brand image and examines the role of influencer reputation and authenticity.

We employed a quantitative method, selecting 245 social media users to complete standardized online questionnaires. Data analysis utilized statistical techniques for objectivity. Using the skincare brand Nivea as a case study, the research investigates how influence marketing strategies affect consumer perceptions.

Our findings show that influencer marketing can enhance brand image, increasing awareness and positive perceptions, provided influencers are seen as authentic and credible. These insights contribute to the ongoing discussion on the efficacy of influencer marketing.

This research contributes to understanding the dynamics between influence marketing and brand image in the modern marketplace.

Keywords: Influence marketing, Social media, Brand image, Advertising campaigns

Introduction

Marketing is everywhere, influencing our daily lives. It affects the clothes we wear, the websites we visit and the advertisements we see...

Marketing involves recognizing and responding to human and social needs. One of the simplest definitions is meeting a need in a profitable and advantageous manner.

There are several types of marketing, including digital, influencer, relationship, street, sports, sensory, experiential, and others.

Influencer marketing is a new phenomenon that has emerged in Morocco and worldwide. It is characterized by the rise of social networks and the disruption of traditional marketing models that have been in place for over a century. Literature on the subject shows that the development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the enormous success of social networks such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube have contributed to the creation of new and innovative marketplaces.

This new market is defined by the exchange of information between companies and their customers through intermediary agents and digital platforms.

Interpersonal interactions and informal sharing of consumption experiences profoundly influence consumer decision-making. Such interactions have a remarkable influence on consumer behavior.

In its Global Trust in Advertising report, Nielsen (2015) asserts that 83% of consumers trust recommendations from friends and family across all forms of advertising, proving that word of mouth is an effective marketing tool.

According to Zouïten (1998), the globalization of markets has had several effects on the production and marketing of consumer goods. This openness to international markets forces companies to make decisions not only in terms of pricing policies, distribution networks, and production locations but also in terms of brand image. With more competitors and products in the market and shorter product life cycles, companies must effectively position their brand image to stand out from intensifying competition and increase consumer awareness and recognition.

Researchers and practitioners recognize the role of brand image as an essential tool to effectively differentiate and manage brands (Aaker, 1996; Joachimsthaler & Aaker, 1999; Kapferer, 2008; Keller, 2008).

Branding literature has tended to define brand image as an internal construct that emanates unilaterally from the organization— what managers want the brand to be—and that requires stability over time (Aaker, 1996; Kapferer, 2008).¹

For all these reasons, we want to use this research to show how a company's influence marketing strategy influences consumer behavior through opinion leaders who are influencing.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine the impact of influence marketing on the brand image perceived by consumers using the example of the Nivea brand. Nivea is an international brand specializing in skincare products, with a recognized and long-standing presence in the market.

Thus, our issue is to answer the following question: "How do advertising campaigns on social media influence consumers decisions regarding brand image?"

To clarify my research approach, it is essential to formulate and explore different hypotheses that will serve as the basis for my investigations.

Hypothesis 1: Influence marketing impacts brand image.

Hypothesis 2: Influencer's reputation can reinforce brand perception.

Hypothesis 3: The authenticity of an influencer affects the credibility of product and service recommendations.

In this sense, this article comprises two main parts: the first part focuses on influence marketing and brand image theory, while the second part addresses the study's methodology and results.

1. Influence marketing

In a constantly evolving communication world, brands must demonstrate creativity to develop effective processes that can reach demanding consumers who dislike intrusive advertising. In this case, influencers adds credibility to campaigns through a more credible and targeted message.

In this chapter, we will delve into the concept of influence marketing, explore various consumer typologies, and examine the levers of influence marketing.

1.1.From Marketing to Influence marketing

The term "marketing," originating from the United States, etymologically means, "to bring to the market". Marketing has given rise to numerous definitions since its inception. These definitions may differ in form but converge in content.

¹ Da Silveira, C., Lages, C., & Simões, C. (2013). Reconceptualizing brand image in a dynamic environment. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(1), 28-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.07.020>

The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines marketing as the process of creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that provide value to customers, clients, partners, and society.

A. Ollivier and R. de Maricourt proposed this definition: "Marketing is at the same time a state of mind, a method a set of techniques to conquer and then maintain a profitable clientele."

From these definitions, we observe that marketing is a mindset, a set of tools used by companies to influence behaviors, identify needs, and respond to consumers desires more effectively than their competitors. There are many different types of marketing, but they all share the same objective: selling products and services, retaining customers, and identifying new consumers and clients.

Among these types of marketing, we will focus on one of these types to better understand and detail it. This type of marketing is influence marketing. We will now move on to an introduction to influence marketing.

1.2.Introduction to Influence marketing – Influence marketing in Morocco

Today, approximately one-third of the world's population uses social media, making it a part of their daily lives. Several authors emphasize that information sharing with the growth of social media has a significant impact on consumer behavior and purchasing decisions.

Search algorithms now control the types of information consumers have access to, and bloggers and opinion leaders can influence purchasing decisions through recommendations shared via social networks.

Lovebrek et al. (2013) describe how the Internet's capability empowers consumers by increasing access to information, choices, and options. This leads to a transfer of power from brands to consumers, making it more difficult for brands to control their marketing messages on social media. These definitions help explain why companies have less control over their brand messages than they did before the era of social media.

Another key finding from the report is that influencers gets a positive image among internet users and are followed by 75% of Moroccans on social networks. The main themes are humor, cooking, technology, and fashion.

1.3.Consumer Typologies

Consumer typologies and product categories are important concepts in marketing. They help us classify and understand consumer buying behavior and preferences to develop more targeted offers and marketing strategies.

Among these consumer typologies:

❖ Loyal Followers:

Consumers who regularly and actively follow influencers, engage with their content, and accept their recommendations.

❖ Explorers (Discoverers):

These consumers are attracted to new influencers and are willing to try new products and services recommended by them.

❖ Skeptics:

They hesitate to accept influencers' recommendations and are more likely to conduct their own research before making a purchase decision.

❖ Occasionally Influenced by Influencers:

These consumers are sometimes influenced by influencers' recommendations but do not always base their purchase decisions on influencers.

❖ Brand Advocates:

Consumers who are particularly attached to a brand or product and tend to follow and support influencers who share their preferences.

❖ Discount Seekers:

These consumers follow influencers to obtain discount codes and special offers and aim to achieve potential savings.

❖ Expertise Seekers:

These consumers seek influencers capable of providing detailed information and critical opinions on products and services before making a purchase decision.

❖ Trendsetters:

These consumers seek the latest trends and influencers who display new products and innovations.

❖ Socially Responsible Consumers:

These consumers are interested in influencers who promote products and brands that align with their social and environmental values.

❖ Lifestyle-Inspired Consumers:

These consumers follow influencers who share a similar lifestyle and provide advice and ideas for adopting that lifestyle.

These influence marketing consumer typologies can help brands better understand how different segments of their audience interact with influencers and create more targeted and effective collaboration strategies.

After exploring different consumer typologies, understanding how consumers interact with influencers becomes crucial in devising effective influence marketing strategies.

1.4. Influence Marketing Levers

Several levers of influence marketing are utilized and can be managed by influence marketing agencies.

❖ Buzzkit:

The company sends its new product to an influencer for testing and sharing their opinion with their community to promote the product. This principle can be linked to unboxing, which also helps introduce the product.

❖ Unboxing:

This phenomenon has gained traction in the United States, where the influencer typically unpacks the product in front of the camera. Unboxing involves unpacking the products received live and sharing this experience with the community. It is based on emotion.

❖ Sponsored Content:

This technique involves sponsoring blog articles and social media posts to reach a maximum number of people and raise awareness. Sponsored articles are the best medium for brands when it comes to gaining recognition.

❖ Product Placement:

This technique is primarily used on YouTube, using the services of YouTubers specializing in topics related to brands' universes.

❖ Travel Blogging:

Travel bloggers are popular, and some have built a very active community. Different travel companies use these types of influencers to promote their products to gain recognition. Travel influencers are often offered all-inclusive stays. Their mission is to take a few photos each day and share them on the blog and especially on social media platforms like Instagram. The biggest travel influencers capture drone-shot videos.

❖ Takeover:

This technique involves giving influencers control of a company's account or brand. A specific period is set to attract community attention to a product, service, event, or website. It all depends on the goals of this campaign.

Regardless of the industry, it is time to embrace influence marketing and deliver a more authentic message to a brand-new community. This community forms an opinion on the brand image, which we will explore next.

2. Brand Image

In today's business landscape, it is crucial not only to retain loyal customers but also to win back those who are on the brink of leaving. Customer segmentation helps identify our most devoted customers and those who only sporadically engage with our platform or e-commerce site, perhaps just to redeem coupons or seek discounts. These occasional visitors can be considered one-time patrons.

The brand image, which reflects how potential and existing customers perceive our business, is pivotal. A positive brand image yields numerous benefits in both the short and long terms. In the short term, a favorable impression can lead to increased sales, with satisfied customers potentially becoming repeat buyers. Over time, this can foster brand loyalty, prompting customers to explore our product portfolio and thus further boosting sales and revenue. Ultimately, expanding market share becomes a natural consequence of this positive feedback loop.²

Competition between brands is intensifying. More and more businesses are aware of the importance of branding. The image is both emotional and communicative perception of products and services that helps ensure the company's success.

One of the most important goals of the company in order to profitably operate is to introduce its activities, the offered goods and services to the largest possible number of users, and thus to check their favor and reputation.

Often, only because of a strong positive image can compete in a saturated market and achieve recognition of a product or service. Brand image can be perceived as emotion, which, being an intangible asset of the company, ensures its long-term prosperity. Due to the abundance of brands, the consumer is exposed to many promotional incentives, but he affects the strongest. For the consumer, the value is created by brands that are able to satisfy the main elements: visibility, quality, price, association, brand identity, loyalty, and relationships. The versatility of these elements means that the brand itself must become diverse.³

2.1. Background

A company can be seen and examined from various angles and perspectives. Some people associate the company with its graphical image while others link it with its product range. The pressure on companies to stand out constantly increases due to the ever-increasing competition.

² Rahul, A. K. (2021). The impact of brand image on the customer: A literature review. *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM)*, 9(6), 1667. Accessed from www.ijaresm.com

³ Işoraité, M. (2018). Brand image theoretical aspects. *Integrated Journal of Business and Economics (IJBE)*, 116. Accessed from <http://ijbe-research.com>

However, companies that successfully manage their brand can expect benefits such as advantages of market entry and differentiation over their competitors (Hatch & Schultz, 2008). After 1980, one of the most important developments within branding has been managers' increased awareness of how crucial and valuable it is for a company to have a strong brand (Riezebos, 2003).

This idea first emerged among financial analysts, who equated a strong brand to a company's future income. During the second half of the 1980s, the idea spread to marketers who quickly understood that a brands' value was not to be underestimated, since a strong brand is possibly the most valuable asset of a company (Keller, 2002).

One example that illustrates how powerful a strong brand actually can be is the research concerning consumer preferences regarding Coca-Cola and Pepsi Cola, brought forward by Melin (1997). The results of a blind test revealed that a clear majority preferred Pepsi to Coke. However, if the consumers were aware of what brand they were drinking, a majority as clear as in the blind test, preferred Coke to Pepsi. The conclusion that can be drawn from this is that brand image to a high extent can affect consumer preferences.

2.2. Definition

A brand image is a subjective mental picture of a brand shared by a group of consumers. (Riezebos, 2003, p. 63).

Brand image can be define as the observations around a brand as reflected by the brand association held in consumer's memory Keller (1993), as mentioned in Anwar et al., (2011). It additionally can define as consumer's sentiments and thought regarding the brand Keller (1993), in Erfan & Kwek (2013).

As such, brand picture portrayed as a summary of brand relationship in shopper's mentality that outcome in brand recognition and brand relationship alongside brand state of mind, brand advantages and brand characteristics.

Further, by Kotler (1988), in Meenaghan (1995), has explained brand image as set of customer's beliefs towards the brand.

Moreover, brand image considered a highly important concept when it comes to consumer behavior. Because Dobni and Zinkhan (1990), stated in Cho (2011), that the brand and product choices mostly based on consumer's perspective, feeling or attitude towards the brand image.

On the other hand, if a company is constantly maintaining a positive and ideal image by the public it would results in gaining a better market place and increasing competitive advantage that leads to a higher market share Park et al., (1986), as stated in Stephen L et al.,(2007).⁴

The brand image can be explained as how the customers perceive the brand. It is the key of how consumers make their choices after gathering information about the particular brand and the alternatives (Ataman & Ülengin, 2003).

Figure 1. The process of inductive inference on brand image

Source : Riezebos, 2003, p. 66

This figure describes how brand image is formed through three different inductive processes: marketing communication, consumption experience and social influence.

This model is used since it allows the researches to sort the communicated brand identity variables accordingly to the way it reaches the consumer and influences its brand image. They are further explained below individually.

❖ Marketing Communication

The marketing communication is the part of figure 1 that an organization can fully control, this is one way of how they express and implement their brand identity.

Advertising gives a company the possibility to modify the consumers brand image and steer it in the direction to the brand identity. This is done in order for the brand identity and brand image to be as congruent as possible (Riezebos, 2003).

It is also highly important that the intended message from the company is understood by the consumer, which would affect the image (Baker & Hart, 2008).

The influences of marketing communication are hard to change when established, as the first impression tends to stick. Therefore, much emphasis should be put on how it should be formed, in order to make the best possible impact on the consumer (Riezebos, 2003).

The organization needs to take noise into consideration as well, which is the surrounding distractions such as competitors advertisements (Blythe, 2006). The advertisement need to

⁴ Opatha, M. (2015, December). Definitions of Brand Image. *Journal of Brand Image*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286669619>

stand out to decrease the level of noise as much as possible, in order for the companies to reach the intended consumer range.

According to Ghodeswar (2008), this can be done with a creative advertising campaign that stands out from the competition. Preferably, consumers should have been exposed to the marketing prior to the consumption experiences and before people in their surrounding have shared their opinion (Riezebos, 2003).

❖ Consumption Experiences

Even if the marketing communication has a strong and positive effect on the consumer, the consumption experience still plays a vital role in the image forming of the customer. These two factors should not contradict each other in order for the consumer to have a clear image of the brand since the message which corresponds to the consumption experience would have the greatest effect on the customer (Riezebos, 2003).

If the marketing communicated to the consumer differs from the actual consumption experience, the image would not only be changed in the eyes of the consumer, it would be worsened. Therefore, the marketing communication needs to be exchanged in a truthful way in order to minimize a potential gap between the marketing and the actual experience of a consumer.

❖ Social Influence

Word of mouth is a powerful communication tool which affects the consumer. It has a powerful influence due to the fact that it is a discussion between two or more people, where opinions are stated and is often reflected as having more credibility than other types of communication methods (Blythe, 2006).

Due to the multitude of choices, the word of mouth can be a triggering factor for the potential customer (O'Leary & Sheehan, 2008).

The opinion expressed by others might be forwarded to the consumer and have an impact on the brand image. Hence, social influence can affect the point of view of potential and actual consumers in their thoughts and beliefs about a certain product, service or brand.⁵

2.3. Difference between brand image and brand identity

Roy and Banerjee (2007) state that a brand helps the customer to distinguish one offer from another. A brand is what the marketer creates for the consumer, and it is what the consumer wants to buy. Looking at the brand from these two perspectives, researchers within the area have divided it into two major perspectives: brand identity and brand image, which are two

⁵ Rosengren, A., Standoft, A., Sundbrandt, A., & Boers, B. (2010, May). Brand Identity & Brand Image (pp. 7-13). Accessed from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:326094/fulltext01.pdf> on the 20/03/2024

closely related concepts, and Melin (1997) states that this can cause them to be mixed up. The difference between them is that brand identity refers to how the brand owner wants the brand to be perceived, and brand image is how customers perceive the brand.⁶

Figure 2. Brand Identity and Brand Image

Source : Sonne, H. Brand Identity vs. Brand Image: Does the identity of Kanniston Leipomo match its image? Page 29.⁷

2.4.Attributes and benefits of brand image

Keller (1993) suggests that brand image is constructed of three different forms of brand associations that are present in consumers' minds. Those three forms are attributes, benefits and attitude.

❖ Attributes

Attributes are features that consumers think a product or a service has. Attributes can be categorized in numerous ways, but usually they are divided into product-related attributes and non-product related attributes. Product-related attributes relate to the physical composition of a product or a service and they are also different depending on the product or service. On the other hand, non-product related attributes are external aspects that relate to a product or a service. (Keller 1993)

⁶ Rosengren, A., Standoft, A., & Sundbrandt, A. (2010, May). Brand Identity & Brand Image. Jönköping University.

⁷ Sonne, H. Brand Identity vs. Brand Image: Does the identity of Kanniston Leipomo match its image? Page 29.

There are four different types of non-product related attributes according to Keller (1993) : Price information, Packaging or product appearance information, User imagery, Usage imagery.

Due to price of the product not affecting its function, it is considered as a non-product related attribute. However, it is an extremely important aspect, since consumers have opinions about a brand's prices. (Keller 1993)

Just like pricing, packaging is considered to be a part of non-product related attribute, because it is a part of the purchase and consumption process, hence it does not affect the product itself. (Keller 1993)

Usage and user imagery attributes relate to the consumers' experiences with the brand. Consumers can be affected by advertising or themselves having their own experience with a brand. (Keller 1993)

❖ Benefits

Keller (1993) defines benefits as features, that consumers think that a product can do for them. They are the personal value for the consumers. Benefits can be categorized as follows: Functional benefits, Experiential benefits, Symbolic benefits.

Functional benefits are considered to correspond product-related attributes. They are the most vital part of the advantages of the products. They offer a solution to the needs of the consumers. Experiential benefits also usually correspond to product-related attributes, in the sense that experiential benefits are all about how the products or a service feels like to the consumer.

Whereas, functional and experiential benefits correspond to product-related attributes, symbolic benefits typically correspond to non-product related attributes. Symbolic benefits relate to the consumers valuing the brand and its exclusivity, and that way satisfying their needs.

❖ Attitudes

Brand attitudes describes the consumers' picture of a brand. Overall, picture of a brand usually forms the basis for behavioral patterns for consumers, hence attitudes are incredibly important. According to the Expectancy-Value model, which is a widely accepted theory, brand attitudes are divided into two sections.

The beliefs that consumers have about the product or a service, which means believing that they think a brand has benefits. The other section is the evaluative judgement of those aforementioned beliefs, meaning, if it is good or bad that a brand has those benefits. (Keller 1993)⁸

⁸ Hänninen, K. (2020). Examining Brand Image: How do Finnish Real Estate Companies Conduct and Utilize Brand Image Studies? (Bachelor's thesis, LAB University of Applied Sciences Ltd, Degree Programme in

Figure 3 explains everything previously mentioned that brand image entails.

Figure 3. Dimensions of Brand Knowledge

Source : Keller 1993

3. Conceptual and methodological framework

3.1. Study Context

Our study focuses on the impact of influencer marketing on brand image. With the emergence of social media, this type of marketing has gained considerable momentum, providing brands with a platform to collaborate with influencers to reach a wide audience in an authentic manner. This strategy goes beyond simple product promotion, it aims to associate the brand with values and a lifestyle that resonates with their target audience, thereby strengthening the brand image. However, despite its growing popularity, the actual effectiveness of influencer marketing remains a subject of debate. Therefore, our research focuses on the in-depth exploration of this complex relationship. By closely analyzing how influencers affect consumers' perceptions of brands, we aim to enrich the debate on the true impact of this marketing strategy, providing new perspectives to this ongoing discussion.

To achieve this, we will proceed with the methodological protocol to delve into the method used for our study.

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3.2. General Methodological Protocol

There are several research methods to address a research question. In our study, we have chosen the quantitative method. This method is characterized by:

Sampling: Participants in the study are randomly selected or stratified to represent a specific population.

Data Collection: It is conducted using standardized means such as questionnaires.

Data Analysis: Data are analyzed using statistical techniques.

Objectivity: Results are presented in the form of numbers, graphs, or tables, rather than subjective opinions or viewpoints.

Quantitative studies can be used in various fields such as psychology, sociology, medicine, economics, and political science. They enable us to gather reliable and objective data, test hypotheses, discover causal relationships between variables, and generalize results to larger populations. In summary, quantitative study is a research method that utilizes standardized and validated techniques to collect and analyze numerical data to address specific research questions.

Our choice of methodological approach is based on a positivist epistemological stance, which emphasizes objectivity and the quantification of observed phenomena. By adopting a deductive reasoning mode, we aim to test specific hypotheses about the impact of influencer marketing on brand image. Using a quantitative method through standardized questionnaires allows us to collect precise and measurable data from a large sample of participants. This approach ensures scientific rigor and the possibility of generalizing the results to a broader population, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of our study. In summary, our methodological approach seeks to provide clear and verifiable insights, significantly contributing to the academic debate on the effectiveness of influencer marketing. Therefore, we will provide a better presentation of the chosen measurement instrument.

3.3. Presentation of the Measurement Instrument

The use of reliable and valid measurement tools is essential to ensure the quality of collected data and to ensure that research results are accurate and meaningful.

In our study, we will use a questionnaire to address our research question. Questionnaires are a commonly used instrument in research to gather data from participants. It consists of a series of questions posed to participants to obtain information on a specific subject.

Surveys can be conducted in person, over the phone, via email, or online. They can be used to measure variables such as attitudes, opinions, behaviors, knowledge, and experiences. They can also be structured or unstructured and can be closed (e.g., predefined response options) or open-ended (e.g., open questions that give participants more freedom to respond).

The design of the questionnaire must take into account several factors, including the target group, research context, research objectives, and variables to be measured. It is important to choose clear and unambiguous questions, structure questions logically, and position questions to maintain participants' interest.

The best way to know what consumers really think about a brand is to ask them. An excellent way to understand the impact of influencer marketing on brand image is to conduct a survey on influencer marketing and brand perception.

This survey will help us understand and evaluate this impact. (Appendix 1: questionnaire)

Let's move on to the selected sample for our study.

3.4. Sampling

Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages, depending on the research context. Samples are an important part of scientific research. This allows researchers to collect more representative data from a larger population with relatively high efficiency. However, it is important to understand the limitations of sampling and potential biases to correctly interpret study results.

Since the objective of our study is to determine whether influencers have an impact on brand image, we have chosen the following for our questionnaire:

Target population: Individuals who use social media

Sample size: A sample of 245

To recruit participants, a list of students, friends, and family will be used. Participants will be selected based on their viewing of influencers and their knowledge of the brand. The questionnaire will be administered online, using a secure link sent to participants via email. Participants will be invited to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire will include questions about brand knowledge, influencers, and their impact on them. The assembled data will be treated in a secure, confidential, and anonymous manner.

The brand selected to study our research question is as follows.

3.5. Company Presentation

Nivea boasts a rich history and a unique evolution. Leveraging its image, reputation, and product benefits, it adeptly navigates various platforms to engage with new audiences.

The Nivea brand traces its roots back to 1911, when Dr. Isaac Lifschütz discovered the formula for its iconic cream, a formula subsequently developed by his colleagues. Rapidly gaining renown, Nivea

expanded its product line to cater to both women and men. The brand's visual identity, epitomized by its signature blue tin, has evolved over time, embodying simplicity and instant recognition.

Across social media, Nivea has been able to adapt its presence by establishing dedicated accounts for different regions. In Morocco, for instance, it maintains active profiles on Facebook and Instagram, enjoying a broad following and established trust. Regular posts shows an array of products suited for diverse skin types and ages, fostering engagement with consumers. Through strategic use of hashtags and collaborations with influential figures, Nivea reinforces its connection with the public, often organizing contests to further stimulate community involvement.

3.6. Presentation of Results:

In today's social media-dominated world, influencers play an increasingly significant role in brand promotion and influencing consumers.

To achieve our objectives, we chose to employ a method based on a questionnaire targeting social media users. Social media provides an ideal platform for influencers to disseminate their content and engage with their audience, making them relevant to this study.

The target population of our study comprises individuals who actively use social media. Given the increasing popularity and accessibility of social media, this demographic group represents numerous potential consumers.

We selected 245 individuals as our research sample. The sample size was determined taking into account the resources and time available to conduct the study. A sample of this size is considered sufficient to obtain meaningful and reliable results.

Therefore, the characteristics of the sample for the study on the impact of influencer marketing on brand image are as follows:

- Sample size: 245 individuals
- Selection criterion: Social media users
- Demographic characteristics: Varied; without age, profession, or city restrictions
- Geographic distribution: Includes participants from different cities and countries.
- Selection method: Participant selection was based on their use of social media, regardless of age, profession, or place of residence.

3.7. Empirical Results

Figure 1: Frequency of Social Media Usage

- 82% of consumers use social media daily, 11.3% multiple times a week, 2% once a week, and 4.7% less than once a week.

Figure 2: Primary Social Media Platform Preference

- Instagram is the most used social network with a percentage of 64%, followed by Facebook with 21.3%, then 14% for TikTok, and finally Snapchat with 0.7%.

Figure 3: Daily Time Spent on Social Media

- 30.7% of consumers use social media for 2 to 3 hours per day, 25.3% use it for more than 3 hours per day, 18.7% use it for 1 to 2 hours per day, 16% use it for 30 minutes to 1 hour per day, and finally, 9.3% use it for less than 30 minutes.

Figure 4: Daily Time Spent Watching Influencer Videos

- 22% do not watch influencer videos, while 37.3% of consumers spend less than 30 minutes watching influencer videos each day. Additionally, 18% watch these videos for 30 minutes to 1 hour per day, 12% watch them for 1 to 2 hours per day, 5.3% of consumers watch these videos for more than 2 to 3 hours per day, and finally, 5.3% of consumers watch them for more than 3 hours.

Figure 5: Main Motivation for Social Media Usage

- The main reason for using social media is entertainment, with a percentage of 43.3%. Following this, 30.7% use it to stay informed about current events, 4.7% to share content, and finally, 1.3% to follow brands or influencers.

Figure 6: Use of Social Media for Product or Service Reviews

- Over 50% have occasionally used social media to seek reviews on products or services before purchasing, 38% have frequently used social media to seek reviews, and 10.7% have never used social media to seek reviews on a product or service.

Figure 7: Use of Influencer Recommendations for Purchases

- 55.3% have not purchased a product recommended by an influencer, while 44.7% of consumers have purchased a recommended product.

Figure 8: Types of Products Purchased Following an Influencer Recommendation

- 53.4% of recommended products are beauty products, 28.8% are fashion products, 12.3% are electronics, 4.1% are food products and the rest is divided between clothing and travel.

Figure 9: Perception of the Effectiveness of Using Influencers on Social Media as an Advertising Form

- According to 52.7%, using influencers on social media is quite effective, for 22% of consumers, using influencers is very effective, while for 12.7%, it is not very effective. For 2.7%, it is not effective at all, and 10% are undecided.

Figure 10: Perception of the Sincerity of Influencers in Their Product or Service Recommendations

- 80% believe that influencers are not sincere in their product or service recommendations, while 20% believe that influencers are sincere.

Figure 11: Frequency of Exposure to Influencer Posts on Social Media

- 38.7% see influencer posts on social media several times a week, 32% see them every day, 17.3% rarely see them, 6.7% see them several times a month, and 5.3% see them once a week.

Figure 12: Reaction to Influencer Product/Service Posts

- 48% of consumers are skeptical and cautious about influencer recommendations, 37.3% pay no attention, and 14.7% are interested in the product.

Figure 13: Determining Factor in Choosing to Follow an Influencer on Social Media

- The most important factor for the majority of consumers is the content they share, followed by the influencer's personality, the products or services they promote, the quality of the photos and videos they post, and finally, the number of followers they have.

Figure 14: Awareness of the Nivea Brand

- 98.7% are aware of the Nivea brand, while 1.3% are not.

Figure 15: Impact of Using Celebrities in Influencer Marketing Campaigns on the Perception of the Nivea Brand

- 81.3% believe that using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand, while 18.7% disagree.

Figure 16: Importance of Relevance Between Product and Influencer for the Impact on the Nivea Brand

- 85.3% believe that the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand, while 14.7% do not think it is important.

Figure 17: Impact of Influencer Reputation on the Perception of the Nivea Brand

- 87.3% believe that the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand, while 12.7% believe that the influencer's reputation has no impact on the perception of the Nivea brand.

Figure 18: Sample Distribution by Gender

- 76.7% are female and 23.3% are male.

Figure 19: Sample Distribution by Age

- 67.3% are between 20 and 30 years old, 12.7% are between 31 and 40 years old, 14% are under 20 years old, 4.7% are between 41 and 50 years old, and 1.3% are over 50 years old.

Figure 20: Sample Distribution by Profession

- 58.7% of respondents are students, 25.3% are employees, 12.7% are executives, the remaining respondents hold diverse occupations.

Figure 21: Sample Distribution by Location

- 60.7% live in Rabat, 15.3% in Casablanca, and the rest in other cities such as Marrakech, Agadir, Oujda, Nador, Taourirt, or even other foreign countries.

❖ **Table of main results :**

Questions	Main Answer
1. How often do you use social media?	82% of consumers use social media every day.
2. What is the social media platform you use most often?	The most used social network is Instagram with a percentage of 64%.
3. How much time do you spend on social media each day?	30.7% of consumers use social media for 2 to 3 hours per day.
4. How much time do you spend watching videos posted by influencers each day?	37.3% of consumers spend less than 30 minutes watching videos posted by influencers each day.
5. What is the main reason for your use of social media?	The main reason for using social media is entertainment with a percentage of 43.3%.
6. Have you ever used social media to seek reviews on products or services before purchasing them?	Over 50% have occasionally used social media to seek reviews on products or services before purchasing them.
7. Have you purchased a product recommended by an influencer?	55.3% have not purchased a product recommended by an influencer.
8. If yes, what types of products have you purchased? (If no, skip to the next question)	53.4% of recommended products are beauty products.

9. Do you think using influencers on social media is an effective form of advertising?	According to 52.7%, using influencers on social media is quite effective.
10. Do you think influencers are sincere in their recommendations of products or services?	80% think that influencers are not sincere in their recommendations of products or services.
11. How often do you see posts from influencers on social media?	38.7% see posts from influencers on social media several times a week.
12. What is your reaction when you see a post about a product/service by an influencer?	48% of consumers are skeptical and cautious about the influencer's recommendation.
13. What is the most important factor for you when choosing to follow an influencer on social media?	The most important factor for the majority of consumers is the content they share.
14. Are you familiar with the brand Nivea?	98.7% are familiar with the brand Nivea.
15. Do you think using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand?	81.3% believe that using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand.
16. Do you think the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand?	85.3% think that the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand.
17. Do you think the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand?	87.3% think that the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand.
18. What is your gender?	76.7% are female.
19. What is your age?	67.3% are between 20 and 30 years old.
20. What is your profession?	58.7% of respondents are students.
21. Where do you live?	60.7% live in Rabat.

Source : Myself

After presenting the obtained results, let's move on to the hypotheses discussed at the beginning of our study.

Hypothesis 1: "We assume that influencer marketing impacts brand image."

The results confirm this hypothesis, emphasizing the importance of an influencer's presence in shaping consumers' perceptions of a brand. In our sample, respondents show a clear tendency to be effected by influencer recommendations and content, which significantly affects how they perceive brands.

Hypothesis 2: "We believe that the influencer's reputation can strengthen brand perception."

The results support this hypothesis, showing that an influencer's reputation does indeed enhance brand perception.

Hypothesis 3: "We assume that the authenticity of an influencer affects the credibility of product and service recommendations."

The results of our research do not support this hypothesis. According to respondents, influencers are not sincere and authentic, but sometimes their opinions are considered. Therefore, an influencer's authenticity does not affect the credibility of recommendations.

In summary, the provided data highlights the prevalence of social media in consumers' daily lives and its impact on their purchasing habits. Influencers play a key role in influencing purchase decisions, but there is also skepticism and mistrust towards their recommendations. Brands can capitalize on these trends by working with relevant influencers to create high-quality content to enhance brand awareness and generate positive perceptions.

Conclusion

Influence marketing is a marketing strategy that involves collaborating with influencers to promote products and services to an audience. Influencers are individuals with a strong presence and influence in a specific field on social media. Influence marketing enables brands to reach a broader audience and build trust by leveraging the trust influencers have with their audience. This marketing strategy can be used for various purposes such as increasing brand awareness, customer loyalty, lead generation, and sales.

Partnerships between brands and influencers can take various forms, such as sponsored posts, contests, events, product reviews, promotional videos, etc. It is necessary for these partnerships to be transparent, with the influencer disclosing their collaboration with the brand to promote its product or service. Influence marketing has become a rapidly growing industry costing billions of dollars annually. However, it is important for brands to choose influencers who align with their brand image and to work with them honestly to avoid damaging the brand's credibility.

Brand image is the perception that consumers have of a brand. Brand image represents the personality, value, quality, and image of a company or product in consumers' minds. It is often associated with logos, colors, slogans, packaging, etc., but also encompasses the brand experience, customer interactions, product or service quality, and communication and marketing strategies.

Brand image is important because it can influence consumer purchasing decisions, brand loyalty, and perceptions of brand quality and value. A strong brand image helps companies differentiate themselves from competitors, increase market share, and generate additional revenue. By creating a consistent and memorable visual and verbal identity, offering a quality product or service, providing a positive brand experience, and effectively communicating with the target audience, the brand can improve its image. It is also important to regularly monitor brand image to ensure it remains relevant and aligned with the company's values and objectives. Influence marketing has a significant impact on brand image. By using influencers to promote their products and services, brands can reach a wider audience and build trust with consumers. However, if the influencers involved in the promotion are seen as unreliable or inauthentic, the quality of the brand image may suffer. Therefore, it is important for brands to choose credible and authentic influencers who align with their values and personality.

The study conducted to explore the impact of influence marketing on brand image shows that influence marketing can have a positive impact on brand image, increase brand awareness, generate a more positive perception of the brand, and strengthen consumer trust in the brand.

However, the study also revealed that influence marketing can have a negative impact on brand image, particularly due to the credibility of the influencer and fraudulent or dishonest behavior of some influencers.

In summary, influence marketing can be a powerful tool for building brand image. However, it is important for companies to consider potential risks and take appropriate measures to ensure transparency and credibility in their influence marketing campaigns. o strengthen their brand image and drive business success.

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Abbreviation

ICT : Information and Communication Technologies

AMA : American Marketing Association

Appendices

Appendix 1 : Questionnaire

1. How often do you use social media?
2. What is the social media platform you use most often?
3. How much time do you spend on social media each day?
4. How much time do you spend watching videos posted by influencers each day?
5. What is the main reason for your use of social media?
6. Have you ever used social media to seek reviews on products or services before purchasing them?
7. Have you purchased a product recommended by an influencer?
8. If yes, what types of products have you purchased? (If no, skip to the next question)
9. Do you think using influencers on social media is an effective form of advertising?
10. Do you think influencers are sincere in their recommendations of products or services?
11. How often do you see posts from influencers on social media?
12. What is your reaction when you see a post about a product/service by an influencer?
13. What is the most important factor for you when choosing to follow an influencer on social media?
14. Are you familiar with the brand Nivea?
15. Do you think using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand?
16. Do you think the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand?
17. Do you think the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand?
18. What is your gender?
19. What is your age?
20. What is your profession?
21. Where do you live?

Appendix 2 : Questionnaire answers

Figure 1: Frequency of Social Media Usage

Source : Myself

Figure 2: Primary Social Media Platform Preference

Source : Myself

Figure 3: Daily Time Spent on Social Media

Source : Myself

Figure 4: Daily Time Spent Watching Influencer Videos

Source : Myself

Figure 5: Main Motivation for Social Media Usage

Source : Myself

Figure 6: Use of Social Media for Product or Service Reviews

Source : Myself

Figure 7: Use of Influencer Recommendations for Purchases

Source : Myself

Figure 8: Types of Products Purchased Following an Influencer Recommendation

Source : Myself

Figure 9: Perception of the Effectiveness of Using Influencers on Social Media as an Advertising Form

Source : Myself

Figure 10: Perception of the Sincerity of Influencers in Their Product or Service Recommendations

Source : Myself

Figure 11: Frequency of Exposure to Influencer Posts on Social Media

Source : Myself

Figure 12: Reaction to Influencer Product/Service Posts

Source : *Myself*

Figure 13: Determining Factor in Choosing to Follow an Influencer on Social Media

Source : *Myself*

Figure 14: Awareness of the Nivea Brand

Source : *Myself*

Figure 15: Impact of Using Celebrities in Influencer Marketing Campaigns on the Perception of the Nivea Brand

Source : *Myself*

Figure 16: Importance of Relevance Between Product and Influencer for the Impact on the Nivea Brand

Source : Myself

Figure 17: Impact of Influencer Reputation on the Perception of the Nivea Brand

Source : Myself

Figure 18: Sample Distribution by Gender

Source : Myself

Figure 19: Sample Distribution by Age

Source : Myself

Figure 20: Sample Distribution by Profession

Source : Myself

Figure 21: Sample Distribution by Location

Source : Myself

Appendix 3 : Figures

Figure 1. The process of inductive inference on brand image

Source : Riezebos, 2003, p. 66

Figure 2. Brand Identity and Brand Image

Source : Sonne, H. Brand Identity vs. Brand Image: Does the identity of Kanniston Leipomo match its image? Page 29.

Figure 3. Dimensions of Brand Knowledge

Source : Keller 1993

Appendix 4 : Table

Table 1. Table of main results

Questions	Main Answer
1. How often do you use social media?	82% of consumers use social media every day.
2. What is the social media platform you use most often?	The most used social network is Instagram with a percentage of 64%.
3. How much time do you spend on social media each day?	30.7% of consumers use social media for 2 to 3 hours per day.
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7. Have you purchased a product recommended by an influencer?	55.3% have not purchased a product recommended by an influencer.

8. If yes, what types of products have you purchased? (If no, skip to the next question)	53.4% of recommended products are beauty products.
9. Do you think using influencers on social media is an effective form of advertising?	According to 52.7%, using influencers on social media is quite effective.
10. Do you think influencers are sincere in their recommendations of products or services?	80% think that influencers are not sincere in their recommendations of products or services.
11. How often do you see posts from influencers on social media?	38.7% see posts from influencers on social media several times a week.
12. What is your reaction when you see a post about a product/service by an influencer?	48% of consumers are skeptical and cautious about the influencer's recommendation.
13. What is the most important factor for you when choosing to follow an influencer on social media?	The most important factor for the majority of consumers is the content they share.
14. Are you familiar with the brand Nivea?	98.7% are familiar with the brand Nivea.
15. Do you think using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand?	81.3% believe that using celebrities in influencer marketing campaigns can enhance the perception of the Nivea brand.
16. Do you think the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand?	85.3% think that the relevance between the product and the influencer is important for the influencer's impact on the Nivea brand.
17. Do you think the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand?	87.3% think that the influencer's reputation can influence the perception of the Nivea brand.
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20. What is your profession?	58.7% of respondents are students.
21. Where do you live?	60.7% live in Rabat.

Source : Myself